

Formulation, Developments And Evolution Of Immediate Release Tablet Of Anti-Migraine Drug

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ABSTRACT

The present research study comprises of synthesis and characterization of chitosan conjugates and their utility as superdisintegrants in the preparation of immediate release tablets consisting of naratriptan hydrochloride. The chitosan conjugates were synthesized by conjugation reaction using colloidal silicon dioxide and thioglycolic acid. The chitosan conjugates were characterized by determining the charring point, viscosity and subjected to the analytical tools like FTIR, DSC and XRD analysis. The physical mixture of drug and excipients were subjected for compatibility study by FTIR and DSC spectral analysis. The tablet blends were prepared using various proportions of CSC, CTC, SSG and starch as disintegrants and these blends were subjected for pre compression parameters and the results were satisfactory. The tablets were prepared by direct compression method. The post compression parameters of the compressed tablets were studied and the results were as per the required standards. The tablets consisting of CSC as superdisintegrant consumed relatively less time for the disintegration than with that of SSG, CTC and starch. The mechanism of super disintegration of the synthesized chitosan conjugates and commercially available SSG was established by determining viscosity, pseudoplastic nature, deformation, wicking/capillary property, pore formation ability and wetting time, percentage moisture uptake of the compressed tablets. The results of these parameters suggested that the superdisintegrating property was due to less viscosity of the superdisintegrants, thereby allowing more amount of disintegration fluid to get through the formed micropores and promote swelling and increase in internal pressure of the tablet. The formation of micropores was observed in SEM images.

Keywords: Immediate release tablet, Mechanism.

INTRODUCTION

Various formulation strategies were explored to achieve a rapid start of action and improved compliance from the patient. Several criteria were assessed for the prepared tablets, including drug content, disintegration time, dissolution profile, and stability. The optimized formulation exhibited promising characteristics, suggesting its potential as an effective treatment option for migraine patients. Migraine immediate-release tablets are designed to provide immediate relief from migraine symptoms. Most of these include drugs such as sumatriptan, zolmitriptan or rizatriptan, and Eletriptan, which acts as a vasoconstrictor constrict blood vessels in the brain and block pain pathways. These tablets are

designed to be taken at the start of a migraine attack for quick relief. The immediate-release tablets were made with Eletriptan hydrobromide as the active pharmaceutical component. The direct compression method was used together with the proper excipients to create the tablets. Several formulation parameters were adjusted to achieve the desired drug release kinetics, disintegration time, and mechanical strength. Among other things, the tablets' thickness, hardness, friability, disintegration time, and in vitro drug release were evaluated. All things considered, the recently developed Eletriptan hydrobromide immediate-release tablets serve as an effective treatment choice for the acute management of migraine, improving patient compliance and providing prompt relief from migraine symptoms.[1] In migraine, there are attacks

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of moderate to severe, frequently one-sided pulsating-throbbing headache which increase in intensity on physical activity.⁸ One-third of the patients suffer holocranial headache. The individual attacks are accompanied by lack of appetite (almost always), nausea (80%), vomiting (40–50%), photophobia (60%), sensitivity to noise (50%) and hypersensitivity to certain odours (10%). Signs of activation of the parasympathetic system are observed in up to 82% of the patients, most often mild watering eyes. When the head pains are one-sided, they may change sides during an attack or from one attack to another. The intensity of the attacks may vary markedly from attack to attack. The duration of the attacks, according to the definition of the International Headache Society (IHS), is between 4 and 72. In children, the attacks are shorter and may manifest without headache, with only severe nausea, vomiting and dizziness. The localization of the head pain is more often bilateral. [2] The oral route is one of the most preferred routes of drug administration as it is more convenient, cost effective, and ease of administration lead to high level of patient compliance. The oral route is problematic because of the swallowing difficulty for pediatric and geriatric patients who have fear of choking. Patient convenience and compliance-oriented research has resulted in bringing out safer and newer drug delivery systems. Various bioadhesive mucosal dosage forms have been developed, which includes adhesive tablets, gels, ointments, patches, and more recently the use of polymeric films for buccal delivery, also known as mouth dissolving films. The surface of buccal cavity comprises of stratified squamous epithelium which is essentially separated from the underlying tissue of lamina propria and submucosa by an undulating basement membrane. It is interesting to note that the permeability of buccal mucosa is approximately 4-4,000 times greater than that of the skin, but less than that of the intestine. [3] The rationale of this investigation is to design an immediate release oral dosage of Sumatriptan succinate by using microcrystalline cellulose as filler, camphor and menthol as subliming agents by direct

compression method. The basic objective of this dissertation is to develop an or dispersible tablet of sumatriptan succinate used in anti- migraine with an aim of reduces the lag time and providing faster onset of action to relief the acute migraine effect immediately. Disintegrates and disperses in oral cavity within 30 seconds without the need of drinking water. Has pleasant mouth felt and there is no after taste or grittiness. Successfully discriminates the ability of three super disintegrants to promote drug dissolution and proposes a model formulation for disintegrants performance testing and quality control purposes. The formulation F6 containing 8% of CCS and 10% of menthol showed disintegration time of 18seconds after drying. Menthol as subliming agent was found to be most effective of all other subliming agents as it had showed drastic effect on the drug release. Sublimation is the process of transformation directly from the solid phase to the gaseous phase without passing through an intermediate liquid phase. Sublimation is an endothermic phase transition that occurs at temperatures and pressures below a substance's triple point in its phase diagram. At normal pressures, most chemical compounds and elements possess three different states at different temperatures. In these cases, the transition from the solid to the gaseous state requires an intermediate liquid state. Note, however, that the pressure referred to here is the partial pressure of the substance. [4] Oral routes of drug administration have wide acceptance up to 50-60% of total dosage forms. Solid dosage forms are popular because of ease of administration, accurate dosage, self-medication, pain avoidance and most importantly the patient compliance. The most popular solid dosage forms are being tablets and capsules; one important drawback of this dosage forms for some patients, is the difficulty to swallow. Drinking water plays an important role in the swallowing of oral dosage forms. Often times people experience inconvenience in swallowing conventional dosage forms such as tablet when water is not available, in the case of the motion sickness (kinetics) and sudden episodes of coughing during the common cold, allergic condition and bronchitis.[5]

Fig. No. 1: Migraine vs Headache: Key Differences You Need to Know

Migraine is considered as a neurological disease or disorder that is characterized by recurrent moderate to severe headaches along with symptoms of autonomic nervous system. Bi-layered tablet is an alternative to the oral drug administration. This system is mainly used to administer fixed dose combinations of different APIs are prolong the drug product life cycle and fabricate novel drug delivery systems such as Chewing device, Buccal Mucoadhesive delivery systems and Floating tablets for gastro-retentive drug delivery. They help to control the delivery rate of single or different active pharmaceutical ingredients.[6] In the late 1970s, oral-dissolving drug delivery systems had been first introduced as an alternative to conventional tablets. Sublingual drug delivery produces quick onset of action, better bioavailability, and maximizes dissolution properties. The benefit of the sublingual system is that the drug can directly reach the bloodstream and bypass the enzymatic degradation in the liver and stomach. The above benefits lead to enhanced bioavailability of the drug in the blood, as compared to that with conventional tablets. This type of formulation brings great benefit in the case of pediatric, geriatric patients, and non-compliant patients. The major problems associated with orally ingested tablets are first-pass metabolism, bioavailability, and the onset of drug action.[7] The oral drug administration route is the oldest and most suitable route of drug administration. The oral cavity is highly enriched with blood capillaries and is more permeable to low molecular

drugs than any other route. This route can be used for both systemic and localized effects. However, this route encounters limitations, such as swallowing distress, especially in conditions, such as vomiting, dysphasia, and Parkinson's disease. At least 28% of the overall population showed uneasiness consuming the solid dosage form. In the 1970s, a new dosage form was introduced to overcome these disadvantages and was termed fast dissolving films (FDF). These films are prepared using hydrophilic polymers that become hydrated and stick in the oral cavity upon encountering salivary fluids. After hydration, these polymers disintegrate the drugs in the oral cavity due to a network of capillaries in sublingual mucosa, causing an increase in systemic absorption of the drug. [8] Migraine is currently the sixth most prevalent disease globally, and it is a major cause of disability, which imposes an enormous personal and socio-economic burden. [17]

Advantages of the bi-layer tablet:

Pharmacological therapies either require or benefit from the administration of drugs in a sequential manner. These combined formulations function from a single dosage form, which simplifies the therapy and reduces or eliminates the chances of improper administration. Bilayer formulations carry more than one drug and deliver each of them without any pharmacokinetic or dynamic interactions, with their individual rate of delivery (immediate, timed or sustained). Bilayer tablet technology is improved

beneficial technology to overcome the shortcoming of the single layered tablet. The manufacture of bilayer tablets, produced by sequential compaction of loose powder layers has become an increased interest within the pharmaceutical industry due to tailored release of active ingredients that may be obtained. Several pharmaceutical companies are currently developing bi-layer tablets, for a variety of reasons: patent extension, therapeutic, marketing to name a few. To reduce capital investment, quite often existing but modified tablet presses are used to develop and produce such tablets. Despite their advantages, due to the use of different materials and complex geometric boundaries between the adjacent layers, the mechanical structures of this drug delivery system have become quite intricate, requiring complicated tablet architectures as well as patient- friendly administration which pose serious challenges to the pharmaceutical scientists/engineers.

1. These are the solid unit dosage forms and have greater capability amongst all oral dosage forms.

2. As compared with various other dosage forms, their cost is very low.

3. It is compact and lighter.

4. For packaging and stripping, it is easiest and cheapest.

5. It is very much easy for swallowing and least tendency to hang-up.

6. Coating technique helps to mask the objectionable Odor and bitter taste masking.

7. It is very much suitable for production on a large scale.

8. It has a very high chemical stability and microbial stability. [21]

Disadvantages of bi-layer tablet:

Throughout the years of research aimed to develop new dosage form of zero order or nearly zero order

kinetic, a variety of oral dosage forms have come about. This hold modified release properties, and include such forms as film coated capsules, pellets or tablets, compression- coated tablets, systems using electrostatic deposition, osmotic or ion-controlled systems, technology three-dimensional (3D) printing dosage forms. Miscellaneous release profiles e.g. delayed release, pulsatile or multimodal delivery profiles, may be attained using changes in the composition, combination of layers or the geometry of multi-layer tablets. Monolayer and multi-layer tablets are produced by compacting powder substances under compression force. The manufacture of a multi-layer tablet is a delicate process, yet it has many common technological features. In a situation of paediatric and insensible subjects, it is very difficult to administer.

1. Dense compacts, amorphous nature and low-density character are found in certain drugs.

2. Drugs which have slow dissolution, poor wetting, ideal absorption in the Gastro Intestinal Tract, faces difficulty in formulation and manufacturing into a tablet.

3. Encapsulation or coating is required for bitter tasting drugs, drugs with an objectionable odor or drugs that are sensitive to oxygen. [22]

Types and causes of hypertension:

Essential and secondary hypertension are the two types of hypertensions. The main causes of hypertension are as follows:

1. Renal: Acute glomerulo-nephritis Chronic renal disease Polycystic disease, etc.

2. Endocrine: Adrenocortical hyper-function Exogenous hormones Pheochromocytoma.

3. Cardiovascular: Contraction of aorta Increased cardiac output Rigidity of the aorta.

4. Neurologic: Psychogenic Acute stress, including surgery Sleep apnea. [23]

Fig. No. 2: Types of Headaches Primary Headache & Secondary Headache

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The following materials and chemicals, as depicted in Table 3, were utilized during the research work.

Materials Used in Present Study-

Sr. No.	Materials	Manufacturer/ Supplier
1.	Metoprolol tartrate	Thyone Pharmaceuticals, Vishakhapatnam
2.	Indapamide hemihydrate	Dishman Pharmaceuticals and Chemicals, Ahmedabad
3.	HPMC	Colorcon Asia Pvt. Ltd, Greater Noida
4.	Microcrystalline cellulose	Kowa India Pvt. Ltd., Ahmedabad
5.	Starch	Colorcon Asia Pvt. Ltd, Greater Noida
6.	Lactose	Madhu Hydrocolloids Pvt. Ltd, Ahmedabad
7.	Croscarmellose sodium	Gloria Interchem Pvt.Ltd., Vadodara

LIST OF EQUIPMENTS

The following equipment's as depicted in Table 4, **List of instruments used Table 4** were utilized during the research work.

Sr. No.	Instruments	Manufacturer
1.	Weigh balance (Electronic)	Shimadzu
2.	UV-1800 double beam spectrophotometer	Shimadzu, Japan
3.	FTIR- infrared spectrophotometer	Shimadzu
4.	DT apparatus	Prolab, Mumbai
5.	DSC	Shimadzu DSC-60 Plus Thermal Analyzer, Japan
6.	Tablet punching machine (12 station)	Delite Tablet Punching Machine, Vadodara
7.	Friability test apparatus – Roche friabilator	Meta Lab Scientific Industries, Mumbai India
8.	Digital Vernier Calliper (0.01mm Least Count)	Bliss Classic, Bangalore

9.	Disintegration test apparatus	DBK Instruments, Mumbai
10.	Monsanto hardness tester	Pathak Electrical Works, Mumbai
11.	Hot air oven	Bioline Technologies Kalwa West, Thane
12.	Stability control oven	Accurate Scientific Danilimda, Ahmedabad
13.	Tap density Apparatus	Campbell Electronics, Mumbai, India
14.	Dissolution tester (TDT-14L USP)	Electrolab, Bangalore, India

PREFORMULATION STUDIES OF DRUGS (Metoprolol tartrate and Indapamide hemihydrate):

Calibration curve of drugs:

The calibration curve of metoprolol tartrate was prepared by using pH 1.2 HCl buffer and for indapamide hemihydrate it was prepared by using pH 1.2 HCl and pH 7.2 phosphate buffer and determined using a UV spectrophotometer.

FTIR study:

Bulk drugs were identified by using FTIR Spectrophotometer. KBr pellet technique was utilized for sample analysis. Hydraulic pressure was used for preparing drug pellets. The wave number range of 400-4000 cm^{-1} was used.

Determination of particle size and particle size distribution:

For many active substances, particle size has an impact on powder flow, content uniformity and drug dissolution. In order to assure consistent product quality, the particle size of the API had been characterized. The particle size of Metoprolol tartrate and indapamide hemihydrate was analysed by Malvern Mastersizer, which was based on the principle of light scattering, by the dry method. Likewise, the particle size distribution of the powder of both the drugs was determined by electromagnetic sieve shaker apparatus.

Drug-drug interaction study:

DSC and FTIR techniques were used for the study of drug-drug interaction as well. Initially the samples were heated at 50 to 4600C. Ampoules were washed

with water and acetone and sealed with samples (metoprolol tartrate, indapamide hemihydrate and mixture of metoprolol tartrate + indapamide hemihydrate) as shown in Table 4. Then these samples were kept for 28 days in the stability chamber. These samples were scanned at 50 to 4000C and thermograms were obtained.

Bulk density:

A weighed quantity of powder (25 gm) was introduced into the measuring cylinder and then the initial volume was noted. Bulk density was expressed in g/ml and determined by the following formula:

$$\text{Bulk Density} = (\text{Dry Soil Weight}) / (\text{Soil Volume})$$

Tapped density:

This gave a new volume (V_f). If the difference between V_o and V_f was more than 2%, another 1250 taps were given, until the difference was reduced to less than 2%. Tapped density was then calculated from the following formula:

$$\text{Tapped Density} = \text{Mass (M)} / \text{Tapped Volume (Vf)}$$

RESULTS OF DIFFERENT BATCHES OF IMMEDIATE RELEASE TABLETS OF METOPROLOL TARTRATE:

Pre-compression parameters of powder blends of metoprolol tartrate immediate release tablets:

The granules prepared were evaluated for their physical characteristics. The evaluation was carried out using the parameters such as bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio and angle of repose, as per the method described under preformulation studies. The micromeritic properties

of powder blends of preliminary batches are shown in Table 18

Batch	Angle of Repose (°)	Bulk density (g/mL)	Tapped bulk (g/mL)	Compressibility Index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
A1	29.58±0.18	0.28±0.17	0.30±0.029	14.59±0.016	1.10±0.04
A2	30.56±0.14	0.28±0.16	0.31±0.028	8.88±0.012	1.12±0.023
A3	30.15±0.15	0.28±0.14	0.29±0.030	12.63±0.014	1.20±0.017
A4	29.35±0.18	0.29±0.16	0.30±0.028	10.48±0.015	1.16±0.016
A5	30.45±0.19	0.28±0.13	0.31±0.027	8.37±0.017	1.18±0.05
A6	31.82±0.16	0.28±0.17	0.30±0.029	7.55±0.018	1.19±0.016
A7	30.55±0.14	0.27±0.18	0.29±0.028	8.52±0.016	1.10±0.012
A8	29.45±0.16	0.29±0.19	0.30±0.025	11.02±0.014	1.09±0.007
A9	30.59±0.17	0.30±0.17	0.31±0.026	10.56±0.013	1.08±0.006
A10	31.25±0.19	0.31±0.18	0.30±0.023	9.15±0.015	1.03±0.004

CONCLUSION & DISCUSSION:

The immediate dissolving tablet dosage form offers a fast release of drug beneath the route and it reaches the systemic circulation directly with improved patient compliance particularly for those who have difficulty in swallowing. From the above results, we can conclude that 3% of gives an immediate release of drug as compared to another formulation batch. Drug is used in the treatment of Antimigraine. The quick onset of action is desirable in the acute treatment of these disorders. From the present investigation, it can be concluded that fast-dissolving sublingual film formulation can be a potential novel drug dosage form for pediatrics, geriatrics and also for the general population. The formulation in form of bilayer tablet with 1st layer of immediate release part of a selective β -1 blocker (Metoprolol tartrate) while second layer of sustained release part of a diuretic drug (Indapamide hemihydrate)..

REFERENCES

1. Mr. Narsuba D. Dhavle, Dr. Santosh Tarke, Dr. Gitanjali Chavan, Mr. Vishal Sakhare, Ms. Ashwini Gholkar, Mr. Rushikesh Hingmire. Department of Pharmaceutics, SBSPM's B.Pharmacy College, Ambajogai, Beed, Maharashtra, India 431517, "Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Immediate Release Tablet of Eletriptan Hydrobromide An Antimigraine Drug" Journal of University of Shanghai for Science and Technology, ISSN:1007-6735.
2. Hans-Christoph Diener¹, Dagny Holle-Lee¹, Steffen Na²gell¹, Thomas Dresler^{2,3}, Charly Gaul⁴, Hartmut Go⁵ bel⁵, Katja Heinze-Kuhn⁵, Tim Ju⁶rgens⁶, Peter Kropp⁷, Bianca Meyer⁷, Arne May⁸, Laura Schulte⁸, Kasja Solbach⁹, Andreas Straube¹⁰, Katharina Kamm¹⁰, Stephanie Fo¹⁰rderreuther¹⁰, Andreas Gantenbein¹¹, Jens Petersen¹², Peter Sandor¹¹, and Christian Lampl¹³, Treatment of migraine attacks and prevention of migraine: Guidelines by the German Migraine and Headache Society and the German Society of Neurology, Clinical & Translational Neuroscience January–June 2019: 1–40 ^a The Author(s) 2019 Article reuseguidelines: sagepub.com/journals-permissions DOI: 10.1177/2514183X18823377 journals.sagepub.com/home/ctn.
3. 1*Ramji Kurmi, 2Dr. Kuldeep Ganju, 3Devendra S. Lodhi and 4Khushi Chouksey 1Sagar Institute of Pharmacy and Technology (SIPTec) Opposite International Airport Jaipur Road Gandhi Nagar Bhopal Madhya Pradesh India-462036. 2Professor and Principal, Sagar Institute of Pharmacy and Technology (SIPTec) Opposite International Airport Jaipur Road Gandhi Nagar

- Bhopal Madhya Pradesh India-462036. 3,4Asso. Professor Sagar Institute of Pharmacy and Technology (SIPTec) Opposite International Airport Jaipur Road Gandhi Nagar Bhopal Madhya Pradesh India-462036, Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Fast Dissolving Oral Film of Anti-Migraine Drug, World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research www.wjpmr.com, wjpmr, 2022, 8(1), 150 – 160.
4. P. Munija*, G. Srikanth, Department of pharmaceuticals, Vision College of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research Boduppall, Hyderabad, Telangana, India, Formulation and Evaluation of Sumatriptan Immediate Release Tablets, Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics Open Access to Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, Received 25 July, 2018; Review Completed 07 Sep 2018; Accepted 109 Sep 2018; Available online 15 Sep 2018, <http://dx.doi.org/10.22270/jddt.v8i5.1904>.
 5. Kamal Kant Ravi, *Kapil Kumar, Gurleen Kaur and Deepak Teotia, Division of Pharmaceutics, Global Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Affiliated to Uttarakhand Technical University, Kashipur-244713, India, Formulation And Evaluation Of Floating Tablet Of Rizatriptan Benzoate, International Journal of Modern Pharmaceutical Research, www.ijmpronline.com, IJMPr 2021, 5(5), 01-0.
 6. A. Madhusudhan Reddy*, J. Sindhura, B. Naga Lakshmi, A. Abhishekar Reedy, D. Navya Sri, M. Nireekshan Kumar and P. Srinivasa Babu, Department of Pharmaceutics, Vignan Pharmacy College, Vadlamudi – 522213, Guntur Dt., Andhra Pradesh, Formulation and evaluation of bilayered tablets of sumatriptan succinate by using hydrophilic polymers, Der Pharmacia Lettre, 2016, 8 (5):189- 206, (<http://scholarsresearchlibrary.com/archive.html>)
 7. Manish Kumar Singh¹, Rupa Mazumder¹, Swarupanjali Padhi¹, Dinesh Kumar Singh² ¹Noida Institute of Engineering and Technology (Pharmacy Institute), Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India. ²Jubilant Generics Limited, Sector-59, Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India, Formulation Development and Optimization of Bioenhanced Sublingual Tablets of Rizatriptan Benzoate to Combat Migraine, Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Education and Research | Vol 56 | Issue 2 (Suppl) | Apr-Jun, 2022, Singh, et al.: Development of Bio-enhanced Sublingual Tablets of Rizatriptan Benzoate.
 8. Waqar Siddique ^{1,2}, Muhammad Zaman ^{3,*}, Rai Muhammad Sarfraz ^{1,*}, Muhammad Hammad Butt ⁴, Atta Ur Rehman ⁵, Noman Fassih ⁶, Ghadeer M. Albadrani ⁷, Roula Bayram ⁸, Mohammad Y. Alfaifi ⁹ and Mohamed M. Abdel-Daim ^{8,10} ¹College of Pharmacy, University of Sargodha, Sargodha 40100, Pakistan ²Department of Pharmacy, University of South Asia, Lahore 54000, Pakistan ³Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Central Punjab, Lahore 54000, Pakistan ⁴Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, Uppsala University, 75123 Uppsala, Sweden ⁵Department of Pharmacy, Forman Christian College, Lahore 54000, Pakistan ⁶Department of Medical Cell Biology, Faculty of Medicine, Uppsala University, 75123 Uppsala, Sweden ⁷Department of Biology, College of Science, Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University, P.O. Box 84428, Riyadh 11671, Saudi Arabia ⁸Pharmacy Program, Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Batterjee Medical College, Jeddah 21442, Saudi Arabia ⁹Biology Department, Faculty of Science, King Khalid University, Abha 9004, Saudi Arabia ¹⁰Pharmacology Department, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Suez Canal University, Ismailia 41522, Egypt * Correspondence: m.zaman2157@gmail.com (M.Z.); sarfrazrai85@yahoo.com (R.M.S.), The Development of Eletriptan Hydrobromide Immediate Release Buccal Films Using Central Composite Rotatable Design: An In Vivo and In Vitro Approach, Polymers 2022,14,3981. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14193981> <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/polymers>.
 9. Rapolu Bharath Kumar^{1*}, Dr.T. Vedavathi² ¹Department of Pharmaceutics, CMR College of Pharmacy, Medchal, Hyderabad, A.P., India, Formulation and Evaluation of Sumatriptan Succinate Oral Disintegrating Tablets and Comparison of Disintegrating Property Between Superdisintegrants and Simpledintegrants, The Pharma Innovation Vol. 1 No. 9 2012 www.thepharmajournal.com Page | 73.

10. Anil Kumar Goyal¹, Mitesh Sharma², Dr. Rajesh Asija³, Seema Yadav⁴ 1,4Maharishi Arvind Institute of Pharmacy, Mansarovar, Jaipur, India. 3 Principal, Maharishi Arvind Institute of Pharmacy, Mansarovar, Jaipur, India. 2Research Scholar, Maharishi Arvind Institute of Pharmacy, Mansarovar, Jaipur, India, Anti- Migraine Fast Dissolving Tablets of Rizatriptan Benzoate, *Corresponding author's E-mail: venousclinical@gmail.com, Received: 15-04-2023; Revised: 23-06-2023; Accepted: 02-07-2023; Published on: 15- 07-2023, Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res., 81(1), July – August 2023; Article No. 23, Pages: 135-141 ISSN 0976 – 044X.
11. Dr M.M Gupta¹, Mayur mahida*¹. Jaipur College of Pharmacy, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.[E-mail: mahidamayur2@gmail.com, Tel: +918690023577], Formulation Development And Evaluation of Immediate Release Tablet of Anti-Hypertensive Drug Olmesartan Medoxomile, The Pharma Innovation – Journal, Vol. 2 No. 3 2013 www.thepharmajournal.com Page | 68, Online Available at www.thepharmajournal.com, Vol. 2 Issue 3 2013.
12. Bhyan Bhupinder*¹, Jangra Sarita²1Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Lovely Professional University, Jalandhar-Delhi G.T. Road (NH-1), Phagwara. Punjab, India. 2Seedling College of Pharmacy, Jaipur National University, Jaipur-302025, Rajasthan, India., Formulation and evaluation of fast dissolving sublingual films of Rizatriptan Benzoate, International Journal of Drug Development &
13. Research | January-March 2012 | Vol. 4 | Issue 1 | ISSN 0975-9344 | Available online <http://www.ijddr.in> Covered in Official Product of Elsevier, The Netherlands SJR Impact Value 0.03,& H index 2 ©2010 IJDDR. R Indira Prasanna, P Anitha, C Madhusudhana Chetty, Department of Pharmaceutics, Annamacharya College of Pharmacy, Rajampet, Andhra Pradesh, India, Formulation and evaluation of bucco-adhesive tablets of sumatriptan succinate, Prasanna, et al.: Buccoadhesive tablets of sumatriptan succinate, International Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation | July 2011 | Vol 1 | Issue 3.
14. Manan Patel¹, Radhika Pandya²1Department of Pharmaceutics, SAL Institute of Pharmacy, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, INDIA. 2Department of Pharmaceutics and Pharmaceutical Technology, L. M. College of Pharmacy, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, INDIA., Formulation and Evaluation of Oral Trans-mucosal Delivery System of Eletriptan Hydrobromide, DOI: 10.5530/ijper.56.3s.149 Correspondence: Prof. Manan Patel Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, SAL Institute of Pharmacy, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, INDIA. E-mail: mananpatel1875@ gmail.com.
15. Majid Tabbakhian^{1,*}, Mohammad Ali Shahtalebi¹, Ehsan Salehi¹, Mahtab Keshvari² 1Department of Pharmaceutics, School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, Isfahan University of Medical Science, Isfahan, Iran 2Isfahan Cardiovascular Research Center, Isfahan Cardiovascular Research Institute, Isfahan University of Medical Sciences, Isfahan, Iran, Formulation and evaluation of orally disintegrating tablet of Rizatriptan using natural superdisintegrant, *Corresponding author: Majid Tabbakhian, School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences. Isfahan University of Medical Sciences, Hezarjerib Ave. Isfahan. Iran. E-mail: tabakhian@pharm.mui.ac.ir, J HerbMed Pharmacol. 2014; 3(1): 21-29.
16. Prasanthi Pakalapati¹, Jiwan Premchand Lavande², Sijo Pattam^{3*}, Prajwal Adhav⁴, Sameer Shafi⁵, Sandeep Nikam⁶, Nilkamal Waghmare⁷, Pranali salunkhe⁸, 1Department of Pharmaceutics, Aditya College of Pharmacy, Surampalem, Kakinada, India 2Department of Pharmaceutics, School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Sanjay Ghodawat University, Atigre, Kolhapur, Maharashtra. 4116118. 3Department of Pharmaceutics, National college of pharmacy, Manassery Calicut 673602. 4Department of Quality Assurance, Abhinav Education Society's College of Pharmacy (B.pharm)Narhe,Pune – 411041. 5Department of Pharmaceutics, Shivlingeshwar College of Pharmacy, Almala, Tq AUSA, District Latur, 413512. 6Department of Pharmaceutics, Bharati Vidyapeeth's College of Pharmacy, Navi Mumbai – 400614. 7Department of Pharmaceutics, Bharati Vidyapeeth's College of Pharmacy, Navi Mumbai – 400614. 8Department of Pharmaceutics, Arvind Gavali College of Pharmacy, Satara, Maharashtra India Pin- 415004. *Corresponding Author: Sijo

- Pattam, Design Formulation and Evaluation of Anti Migraine Mouth Dissolving Tablets Using Different Superdisintegrants * Department of Pharmaceutics, National college of pharmacy, Manassery Calicut 673602. Citation: Sijo Pattam et.al (2024), Design Formulation and Evaluation of Anti Migraine Mouth Dissolving Tablets Using Different Superdisintegrants Educational Administration: Theory and Practice, 3(4), 6393-6404 Doi: 10.53555/kuey.v30i4.2395.
17. Farzin Zobdeh^{1,2} | Aziza ben Kraiem^{1,2} | Misty M. Attwood² | Vladimir N. Chubarev¹ | Vadim V. Tarasov^{1,3} | Helgi B. Schiöth^{2,3} | Jessica Mwynyi², Pharmacological treatment of migraine: Drug classes, mechanisms of action, clinical trials and new treatments, wileyonlinelibrary.com/journal/bph Br J Pharmacol. 2021; 178:4588–4607, Received: 15 January 2021 Revised: 28 July 2021 Accepted: 2 August 2021.
18. Kavya Handenahalli Ramakrishna Reddy and Sayani Bhattacharyya* Department of Pharmaceutics, Krupanidhi College of Pharmacy, No.12/1 Chikkabellandur, Varthur, Carmelaram Post, Bangalore 560035, India, Statistical Optimization and Evaluation of a Multi Release Unit Bilayer Tablet of Rizatriptan Benzoate, January- February 2021, Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Science, 52.
19. Sandeep. A. Wathore, MUPS College of Pharmacy (B. Pharm), Degaon- 444506, Dist. Washim (MS), India Formulation Development and Evaluation of Sublingual Film of Antimigraine Drug www.ijppr.com Human Journals Research Article August 2019 Vol.:16, Issue:1 © All rights are reserved by Sandeep. A. Wathore.
20. Syeda Shazia Nazneen*, S.M Shahidullah Department of Pharmaceutics, Deccan School of Pharmacy, Hyderabad- 500 001, Telangana, India, Bilayer Tablets in Drug Delivery: A Concept of Modified Release, Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res., ISSN: 0976 – 044X, 84(11) – November 2024; Article No. 03, Pages: 19-25, DOI: 10.47583/ijpsrr.2024.v84i11.003, corresponding author E-Mail nazeenshazia31@gmail.com, Received: 16-08-2024; Revised: 02-11-2024; Accepted: 08-11-2024; Published on: 20-11-2024.
21. A Review on Bi-layer Tablets, M. Namrata*, V.N.L. Sirisha, B. Sruthi, I. Bhavani Harika, P. Kirankumar, Y. Kiran Kumar Rao, K. Pranavi, S. Sindhura, N. Vamsi Krishna, O. Uma Maheshwara Rao, Anurag Pharmacy College, Affiliated to JNTUH, Kodad, Dist. Nalgonda
22. Andhra Pradesh, India, Available on line at: www.eijppr.com International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Phytopharmacological Research, ISSN (Online) 2249 – 6084, ISSN (Print) 2250- 1029, Int. J. Pharm. Phytopharmacol. Res. 2013, 2(4): 240-246.
23. Tomasz Blicharski¹, Katarzyna Swiader², Anna Serefko³, Sylwia Kulczycka- Mamona², Michal Kolodziejczyk⁴, Aleksandra Szopa³, ¹ Chair and Department of Rehabilitation and Orthopedics, Medical University of Lublin, Jaczewskiego 8, 20-090 Lublin, Poland, ² Chair and Department of Applied and Social Pharmacy, Medical University of Lublin, Chodzki 1, 20-093 Lublin, Poland, ³ Chair and Department of Applied and Social Pharmacy, Laboratory of Preclinical Testing, Medical University of Lublin, Chodzki 1, 20-093 Lublin, Poland, ⁴ Department of Applied Pharmacy, Medical University of Lodz, Muszynskiego 1, 90-151 Lodz, Poland, Challenges in technology of bilayer and multi-layer tablets: a mini-review, Current Issues in Pharmacy and Medical Sciences, Formerly Annales Universitatis Mariae Curie-Sklodowska, Sectio DDD, Pharmacia, journal homepage: <http://www.curipms.umlub.pl/>, DOI: 10.2478/cipms-2019-0039, Curr. Issues Pharm. Med. Sci., Vol. 32, No. 4, Pages 229-235..

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